

Literature Review: Factors Affecting Labor Productivity

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Abstract:

The purpose of the article is to review the research related to labor productivity. Factors affecting labor productivity. Effects of FDI on labor productivity; The effect of exports on labor productivity and finally the effect of non-wage benefits on labor productivity. The author conducts analysis, evaluation and gives discussion as well as possible research directions in the future.

Keywords: Labor productivity, non-wage benefits.

1. Introduction

In the 1990s of the 20th century, Vietnam's economy had a remarkable growth mainly from increasing labor productivity in agriculture. This is the result of the process of dissolving the cooperative (cooperative) and handing over land use rights to the private sector. In the following years, Vietnam's economic growth was based on the outstanding development of the system of private enterprises (Bodewig and Magnusson, 2014). Jobs have been created for millions of people thanks to the economic restructuring from agriculture to export-oriented service, manufacturing and processing sectors.

Despite clear and steady progress than some other countries, Vietnam is now continuing to face new challenges. The economic growth rate and the transition from the agricultural sector to other sectors show signs of slowing down, and per capita income is low (Vu Minh Khuong, 2016). Productivity growth, which used to be the main driver of Vietnam's economic growth in the early years of doi moi, has gradually declined over the past decade, and the growth rate of labor productivity has slowed down (Nguyen Duc Thanh and Ohno Kenichi, 2018). Instead of improving labor productivity to continue to achieve, capital investment becomes the main source of economic growth in this next period. But according to Bodewig and Magnusson (2014), this is not a sustainable model, suitable for Vietnam to maintain a high growth rate.

In addition, Vietnam's working population continues to increase, but the number of young workers tends to decrease. This means that Vietnam cannot continue to rely on the size of its workforce to succeed as it did in the past, but instead needs to focus on making its workforce more productive. (Bodewig and Magnusson, 2014, ILO, 2015).

Over the years Vietnam has benefited from the "demographic dividend", but now the trend of an aging population makes us reduce this opportunity. Besides, the annual growth rate of the labor force tends to decrease gradually (the labor force growth rate is lower than the population growth rate). The current workforce is about 54.5 million people, but only about 23.67% have qualifications (ILO, 2018). Therefore, in order to avoid the situation of "getting old before getting rich", Vietnam needs to focus on improving labor productivity for the labor force (ILO, 2018).

In developing countries including Vietnam, FDI is considered an important economic vehicle because of the advantages of cheap resources and low labor costs. However, not all countries receive the positive benefits from attracting FDI. According to Haque and Thaku (2013), usually FDI enterprises come from countries with relatively abundant capital with intangible assets such as technological progress or management skills and information of new markets. These are assets that are relatively rare in developing countries, but in contrast developing countries have a relatively abundant labor factor. Therefore, as Mottaleb and Kalirajan (2013) sum up, many previous studies have suggested that developing countries should focus on promoting labor-intensive

industries and exporting them first due to low capital and labor force. relatively abundant labor force. However, both Mottaleb and Kalirajan (2013) and Haque and Thaku (2013) agree that not all developing countries reap the benefits of attracting FDI as well as promoting exports of industries. labor intensive. Typical evidence in the study of Haque and Thaku (2013) is China and India. Both countries are relatively labor-abundant, but have had mixed success in attracting FDI as well as exporting for the labor-intensive industry.

According to some studies such as (Dollar et al., 2005; Mottaleb and Kalirajan, 2013) besides labor and capital factors, the export of labor-intensive products depends on other factors. Therefore, although the enterprises in the labor-intensive industry are the industries with more relative advantages for developing countries like Vietnam, they only focus on attracting FDI as well as exporting to the enterprises. Enterprises in labor-intensive industries or all enterprises that focus on attracting FDI and exporting as Vietnam is currently doing may not bring about the expected effect.

In Vietnam, empirical studies show that the influence of technology adoption (reflected through FDI and exports) is the source of output growth and contributes to an increase in labor productivity. Ngo Hoang Thao Trang (2017), when researching export activities, innovation activities and business environment on productivity of Vietnamese SMEs, shows that enterprises applying innovative activities have a good impact on labor productivity. or Pham's (2018) study on the relationship of FDI spillover to labor productivity and other studies. Therefore, there is little doubt about the impact of FDI and exports on labor productivity. An issue that needs more attention is which method of application is appropriate, because FDI and export have different effects on labor productivity and one of them has a more effective or appropriate impact than the other channels in the economy different applicable conditions.

Although both FDI and exports can influence technology spillovers which in turn increase labor productivity, most of the studies are in Vietnam (Nguyen, 2019; Pham, 2008; Le, 2007, Newman et al., 2017).) recognizes the technology spillover of FDI or exports to labor productivity as two separate channels without considering their impact on the enterprise's labor productivity as two competing international technology diffusion channels (in the case of enterprises because of certain limitations can only choose 1 of 2 methods (receiving FDI or participating in exports) and their differences to enterprises have different characteristics. It is important to consider both channels of technology adoption through FDI or export as they are still seen as key to the success of developing countries, especially new economies such as the Asia-Pacific region. East Asia (Hsu and Chen, 2001) and Vietnam is no exception.

The link between welfare or compensation policies and labor productivity has been reinforced in economic theory (needs theory (Maslow, 1954); expectation theory (Vrom, 1964); two-factor theory (Maslow, 1954); expectation theory (Vrom, 1964); Herzberg, 1987) and a number of other theories).

Several studies (Dreher et al., 1988; Micelli and Lane, 1991; Millea, 2002; Tsai and Yu, 2005; Singh, 2009; Anand et al., 2010) demonstrate that non-wage benefits This contributes positively to the labor productivity of employees and the health of workers has a positive impact on labor productivity and the health of the national economy. These benefits strongly influence the behavior of employees, which is a compelling reason to help them continue to work for business owners as well as they are forced to compete with each other and this leads to lower labor productivity of enterprises increase.

The goal of this article is to review the research on factors affecting labor productivity. From there, future research directions are given.

2. Literature review

2.1. Labor productivity

Productivity is an important measure of the efficiency of an economy. Productivity can be measured at different levels: the economy as a whole, the industry level, the organizational level, the firm level, or the individual individual level.

Syverson (2010) productivity is efficiency in production expressed in terms of how much output is obtained from a given input. Therefore, it is often expressed as a ratio of the input to the output. There are many methods

of measuring productivity, in which labor productivity is one of the most used criteria. Accordingly, labor productivity exploits the extent to which human capital brings value to an economy or firm (Koch and McGrath, 1996).

In addition to the labor productivity indicator, productivity is also measured through capital productivity and total productivity (TFP). Depending on the case and data conditions, the choice to use the yield indicator will be different. Sargent and Rodriguer (2001) argue that the TFP composite productivity indicator is appropriate to consider productivity in the long-term trend of the economy. In contrast, according to Nguyen and Kenichi (2018), when looking at the medium and short term, especially when there is doubt about the growth process or unreliable capital stock data, labor productivity is an appropriate indicator suitable for use.

According to Greenlaw et al (2018), labor productivity is the value that each worker creates per unit of his input. The International Labor Organization (ILO, 2015), defines labor productivity as the total quantity of output produced per unit of labor input (measured by total labor) in a given reference time.

Although productivity is said to be relatively simple in concept, some controversy over the measurement of inputs and outputs arises when calculating productivity from actual data (Syverson, 2010).

The two basic measures to measure output are total output and value added (Cobbold, 2003). If for data at the country level there is no significant difference in the use of these two measures to represent the level of output, then at the micro level the difference increases because of the tendency to use intermediate inputs increase (Cobbold, 2003). According to OECD (2001), the choice of output measurement method depends on the intended use of productivity.

Although preferred by many economists in studies of production across industries and output per worker because it reflects both primary and secondary inputs, the indicator of total output requires significant data availability (Cobbold, 2003). According to Syverson (2010), output measurement should be consistent across all outputs in terms of the same unit of measure, whereas at the micro level most firms produce more than one output and therefore they should be aggregated into a single measure. However, detailed micro data and manufacturing enterprises often do not contain full output data as well as conventional ways to bring about the same type of output. Revenue is seen as a viable alternative in this case (Syverson, 2010). Although this may be acceptable and even the best option, in cases where the difference in product quality is fully reflected in the price, the use of revenue may still be possible. Cause problems whenever there is a price change due to differences in market power among producers (Syverson, 2010).

Value-added output is less affected in the empirical calculation than using revenue or total output in the case of outsourcing or exporting firms (Tomiura, 2007; Cobbold, 2003; OECD, 2001). If the labor productivity indicator depends on total sales per worker, vertically integrated firms (exporters or investors) are likely to be less productive than those that outsource their work. even with identical sales and labor productivity because outsourced businesses use less labor. At this point, the measure of total output does not fully reflect the measured change in labor productivity. In addition, according to Van der Wiel (1999), in terms of profit maximization of the enterprise, the value-added criterion proved to be more suitable for the enterprise's objectives than the total output (revenue) target.

According to Cobbold (2003) in addition to the above advantages, the use of added value as a measure of output also encounters limitations including: conceptual deficiencies, providing misleading estimates of industry growth; and provide misleading estimates of contributions to growth.

For input to measure labor productivity according to Syverson (2011), it is possible to choose to use the number of employees, the number of working hours or some other criteria reflecting labor quality adjustment (wages are often used). used in this last role, based on the notion that wages reflect the worker's marginal product when units are not homogenized).

2.2. Factors affecting labor productivity

According to Greelaw et al. (2018), the labor productivity of employees is affected by 3 groups of factors: (1) Human capital, (2) Technological progress, (3) Economic scale. Specifically:

(1) Human Capital

Human capital is the knowledge, skills and expertise and education that a worker in the economy possesses and accumulates. Usually, the higher the average level of education in an economy, the higher the accumulated human capital and the higher the labor productivity (Greelaw et al., 2018).

(2) Technological advancement

The next factor affecting labor productivity is change and technological progress. Technological advancement is the combination of developments, improvements in knowledge and innovation, and the incorporation of that innovation into the production of new products and services (Greelaw et al., 2018).

(3) Economies of Scale

According to Greelaw et al (2018), the final factor affecting labor productivity is the advantage of scale. Economies of scale are the cost advantages that industries or firms derive from scale.

According to Syverson (2010), when studying labor productivity at the micro level, enterprises realize that labor productivity is directly affected by two main groups: internal and external groups. The internal group includes operational factors in the enterprise such as management practice/talent, quality of labor and capital input, product innovation and organizational structure of internal production units. The company. The second set of factors that deal with environmental determinants will include such factors as the productivity spillovers resulting from knowledge transfer, the degree of competition in the labor and product markets as well as the impact of regulations and policies from outside. Factors of this kind will affect productivity by encouraging manufacturers to become more efficient or, alternatively, by shifting economic activity in a more efficient direction. In addition to the two main groups of factors as above, Micallef (2016) also gives a number of factors that have a double impact like the two groups above, for example, when expanding the market to attract FDI, it is not only an external factor that affects productivity, but also helps domestic enterprises improve their internal management activities (Micallef, 2016) or the strong competition of external labor markets helps promote enterprises to apply new methods. With more effective internal people management practices (Bloom et al., 2012), exporting firms are not only more productive but also less sensitive to exchange rate fluctuations (Di Mauro et al. Ronchi, 2015).

For production function-based studies, especially from Cobb-Douglas (e.g. Globerman, 1979; Blomström and Persson, 1983, Kokko, 1994 and Kokko et al., 1996) in examining the As the determinants of labor productivity at the firm level, capital intensity and labor intensity are of primary concern. These studies suggest that higher levels of capital intensity lead to higher productivity because workers are more equipped with equipment. Labor quality is also another major factor, higher quality labor contributes to a good production force with better qualifications and working performance leading to higher labor productivity.

In addition to the main groups of factors affecting labor productivity classified as above, empirical studies with the topic of labor productivity at the enterprise micro level also provide evidence of the impact of other factors affecting productivity. labor includes factors of firm characteristics, union, industry, age of the enterprise and other factors (Koch and McGrath, 1996; Hsu and Chen, 2000; Roger and Tseng, 2000; Wagner, 2002; Vahter, 2004; Greenaway et al., 2004; Doraszelski and Jaumandreu, 2013; Arshad and Malik, 2015).

2.3. The relationship between FDI and labor productivity

Recent empirical studies show that foreign direct investment has different effects on productivity growth, occurring at the same time and can be direct or indirect (Aitken & Harrison, 1999). ; Lichtenberg & Siegel, 1987; Djankov & Hoekman, 1999; Anderson, 2000; Piscitello, Rabbiosi, 2005; Ng, 2007; Liu, Zhao, 2006; Wacker and Vadlamannati, 2011; Georgescu, 2012).

The impact of FDI on labor productivity can be a positive effect as a result of technology transfer and spillover. There is also a negative competitive effect, which seems to be determined by increased competition from foreign firms (Aitken and Harrison, 1999). Because the total output of local firms is reduced, as they have to separate the market from new entrants, large economies are less likely to suffer from reduced productivity in this way.

The spillover from FDI occurs when the entry or presence of multinational corporations increases the productivity of domestic firms in the host country (Borensztein et al., 1998; Javorcik, 2004). According to Liu, Parker et al. (2001) studying the overall effect of FDI on 41 Chinese electronics industry sub-industries found that the presence of foreign enterprises in the industry helps to increase the labor productivity of the industry. Similar results on the positive impact of FDI on labor productivity have been reported in other studies (Caves, 1974) for the Australian market, Globerman (1979) for Canada also demonstrated that labor productivity of local firms have a positive correlation with FDI. This is also the goal that governments strive to achieve when they create policies to attract FDI because it creates the sustainable development of the country, not just a short-term advantage.

The impact of foreign direct investment increases the average GDP due to the introduction of new production technologies and the implementation of effective management (Tülüce and Doğan, 2014). An increase in labor productivity will occur, if foreign firms have better productivity and they can transfer it to local firms provided that local firms are also able to assimilate effective management practices. the results of these externalities. Absorption capacity, as many authors point out, depends on the initial situation of the host country: the stage of development of the economy and trade regime (Lipsev, Sjöholm, 2004), the level of public capacity minimal technology and expertise of workers from the host country and sustained efforts on the part of the government and private sector to assimilate foreign technology (Djankov, Hoekman, 1999). If the host country does not meet the minimum conditions to open its economy, the effects will be very negative. Inefficient local companies will not be able to face competition and will be forced out of the industry. The positive effect on labor productivity of local enterprises has been demonstrated as a result of foreign direct investment in studies in different countries such as: USA (Lichtenberg and Siegel, 1987), Republic of Czech (Djankov, Hoekman, 1999), Indonesia (Anderson, 2000), Italy (Piscitello, Rabbiosi, 2005), China (Liu, Zhao, 2006) and some other studies.

The benefits of FDI depend on the technological capabilities of local firms to receive more benefits from FDI, domestic firms must possess better technological capabilities to receive benefits from FDI (Blomstrom , 1994). Popescu (2010) studies the impact of FDI on different countries, focusing on differences in labor productivity, concluding that domestic enterprises often increase labor productivity due to the management and technological capabilities they borrow from other countries. Foreign companies are established in their home countries and also because: first they have to protect themselves from new competition and secondly they have to comply with the growing demand coming from new investors. Due to higher labor productivity, foreign companies offer higher wages to their employees. This also determines the wage growth of domestic firms. Local businesses do their best to compete with foreign companies in terms of productivity, wages and skilled workers; Failure to do so will lead to differences in wages and skills in the country. Therefore, FDI has positive aspects (technology transfer, management expertise, job creation, regional development and increased labor productivity) along with negative aspects (wage inequality, skill gap) for host country.

In addition to directly affecting labor productivity, FDI also brings a number of effects to the labor market, indirectly affecting labor productivity. Wacker and Vadlamannati (2011) study the effect of FDI on labor market process optimization. The results show a reduction in labor recruitment processes as a direct result of the negotiation process between the employer and the employee. Georgescu (2012) found that in emerging markets to attract FDI, strategies have been implemented through different measures or means to provide a transparent and friendly business environment. investors, which helps to increase labor productivity. The impact of FDI on the labor market according to Driffield and Taylor (2000) is due to the assimilation of labor to the domestic market leading to an increase in the labor wage of the domestic market. Specifically, the results of the study shows that skilled workers will be paid higher after two years due to increased labor productivity from the assimilation of foreign technology.

Foreign direct investment leads to an increase in labor productivity of domestic enterprises in some cases as studied by Djankov (1999) or Piscitello and Rabbiosi (2005), while there are also cases where it has may have a negative impact on labor productivity. According to De Mello (1999) when studying 17 non-OECD countries

and 15 OECD countries, the impact of FDI on labor productivity is negative. He argued that the reason for this negative relationship could be the host countries' inability to adapt to technological advances used by foreign companies or perhaps the host countries have developed enough to take on these technological advances. In addition, FDI can have a negative impact on local businesses in the sense that the introduction of foreign firms into the domestic market will force local firms to downsize some products. due to higher domestic demand for the products of FDI enterprises (Aitken, 1999).

In the Czech Republic, research by Djankov and Hoekman (1999) has obtained some evidence for different effects of FDI on labor productivity. The biggest benefits are foreign investment flowing into FDI companies (resulting from acquisitions) and subsequently joint ventures. Domestic firms with no foreign involvement operating in the same industry as those firms incur significant costs. Since these enterprises cannot but face competition, in the absence of the ability to adapt the same technology used by foreign firms, the limitation of reducing operations to survive, all lead to lower labor productivity. When supported by the government, through important expenses and regulations, FDI enterprises expect to achieve higher development, while local businesses are often not supported (so as not to do this). disturbance of fair competition), will gradually lose the important playing field. The globalization regime allows only the best to survive, but if this happens too soon, the survivors will mostly come from other countries outside the economy.

Barrel and Pain (1997) and Hubert and Pain (1999) point out the fact that productivity does not improve in the host country because foreign companies only hire foreigners in important, technical positions. high and domestic employment is only used on positions that do not require such a high level of expertise. Therefore, locals do not have access to the know-how that foreign companies do.

Figini and Görg (1999) estimate the impact of multinational firms on wage inequality in the host country. The results demonstrate that the wage gap widens when the appearance of FDI enterprises increases due to two factors occurring simultaneously: the increase in labor productivity due to the impact of technology spillover and the demand for skilled labor.

Separating the effect of FDI, productivity has created skilled jobs from domestic firms, Driffield and Taylor (2000) identify a function of the size of the productivity advantage explaining the above effect. The aim is to assert that the ratio of foreign firms' productivity to domestic firms' productivity (at the sectoral level) is what makes the difference in the impact of FDI from one industry to another.

2.4. Export and labor productivity

The relationship between exports and labor productivity has been a subject of discussion for a long time in the economic literature. Proponents of free trade argue that exports affect firms' productivity because firms in developing countries have better exposure to customers and competitors abroad (Biesebroeck et al, 2005). Many studies have provided empirical evidence for this relationship such as Bernard and Jensen (1995), Aw and Hwang (1995), Bernard and Jensen (1999), Aw et al. (2000), Isgut (2001).

According to Wagner (2007), two hypotheses have been proposed to explain why exporting firms have higher labor productivity than non-exporting firms: (1) due to the problem of self-selection. are more productive firms that will export goods; (2) learning by exporting theory: Knowledge from international buyers (foreign customers, importers) or even international competitors improves productivity businesses when they export goods to foreign countries. Moreover, enterprises entering the international market face fiercer competition and are forced to improve themselves faster to meet the needs and tastes of those who only sell to the domestic market.

Empirical articles have investigated the role of exports in promoting growth in general and productivity in particular, using aggregate data for countries and industries conducted long ago and over time. long. The study of Bernard and Jensen (1999) is one of the pioneers to examine the role of exports at a microscopic level, followed by the trend that researchers worldwide have recently used data firm-level data to study the relationship between exports and productivity to assess the extent and causes of productivity disparities between firms in more microscopic studies.

Wagner (2007) examined micro data on the relationship between exports and firm productivity from 1995 to 2004. He found that more productive firms choose to enter export markets themselves. exports, while exporting does not necessarily improve productivity. This means that, according to Wagner, the self-selection effect is more relevant than the learning effect.

The point of Wagner (2007) is also supported for later studies when studying the case of different countries from industrialized countries such as Spain in the study of Cassiman et al (2007).) or in Germany in Baumann et al (2016); Latin American countries such as Chile in the period 1990-1996 in the study of Alvarez and Lopez (2005), Mexico, Colombia and Morocco in the study of Clerides et al (1998); Asian countries such as China in the period 1988-1992 in Kraay's (2002) study or Indonesia in the 1990-1996 period by Blalock and Gertler (2004), Banri & Ayumu (2013) research for Japanese SMEs . These studies argue that innovation and productivity are important determinants of export performance. This argument shows that firms require high productivity and investment in innovative activities before entering export markets.

Claudio et al (2014) investigated manufacturing companies in Chile. They find that firms with R&D research are more likely to export than firms that do not conduct or conduct R&D research. Similarly, Cassiman and Golovoko (2007) examined the innovative relationship between productivity and exports for Spanish manufacturing firms. They find that innovation and productivity drive firms to export because creative and manufacturing firms can easily afford the costs of entering international markets, which is impossible for less innovative firms and lower productivity (Lopez, 2009; Cassimann et al. 2010).

On the other hand, some studies give research results on the second hypothesis, that is, after entering the export market, firms learn from international buyers as well as competitors that higher productivity. Proof of this hypothesis is provided by Martins and Yang (2009). They carried out a meta-analysis of the learning from exports (LBE) hypothesis on more than 30 articles and determined that exports significantly improve the productivity of firms in developing countries due to their greater gap with technology border. Research by Rhee et al. (1984) describes the role of foreign partners in the early development of Korean manufacturing. The relationship between Korean companies and foreign customers has gone far beyond contract negotiations and implementation. Nearly half of enterprises said they have directly benefited from technical information provided by foreign customers: through visits to their factories by the customer's engineers or other technical staff overseas, through providing design and specifications, through manufacturing techniques and on specifications of competitive products, and through feedback on design, quality, and performance product specifications.

In addition, Trofimenko (2008) studied the learning-through-export hypothesis for 1,057 Colombian manufacturing companies. Trofimenko's research reveals that exporting to advanced countries brings about efficiency gains through information on production methods, product quality and design leading to reduced product costs and thus improved productivity of domestic firms.

Sharma and Mishra (2012) conducted a study on Indian automobile manufacturing enterprises. They analyzed the causal link between exports and productivity by estimating two main hypotheses. First, the self-selection hypothesis, i.e. firms require higher productivity before exporting. Second, the learning-by-export hypothesis is that firms become more productive when they enter export markets. However, their empirical findings only support the export-led learning hypothesis that exports have a positive effect on productivity, but no evidence to the contrary.

Damijan et al (2010) conducted a similar study. They studied the causal relationship between innovation (products, processes) and exports using Slovenian enterprise data. However, the results only found that exporting increased a firm's capacity for process innovation more than product innovation. Their results demonstrated that the export effect takes place through the process innovation mechanism that improves the technical efficiency of the firm and thus leads to high productivity.

According to Martin and Yang (2009), when researching over 30 research articles on the relationship between exports and labor productivity, the author found that the impact of exports on labor productivity was higher in developing countries than in developed countries. developing country.

Several studies comparing research results from countries have found that there are differences in export learning mechanisms in countries from markets with different levels of technology and productivity. Bernard and Jensen (1999) examine productivity growth before and after export market entry of US manufacturing firms. They find that productivity gains precede exports, suggesting self-selection rather than export-induced technological improvement.

According to Blalock (2004), the results of Bernard and Jensen (1999) are not entirely surprising, given the context of US firms where exposure to foreign buyers may be less likely to provide technology. Outperform the technology the United States is using. Clerides et al. (1998) find similar evidence to Aw et al. (2000) when studying for Columbia and Morocco, Taiwan and Korea in the late 1980s and early 1990s, a time when countries has developed successful export-oriented technology industries. In contrast to the above studies, Biesebroeck (2003) examining six sub-Saharan African countries found evidence of learning from exports. These African economies have a much lower level of technology and productivity than the aforementioned countries. Even the same research subject as Korea but at different development periods in the study of Rhee et al. (1984) and Aw (2000) also lead to different results. As a result, exporting can generate larger marginal benefits for firms in markets with less technology and less productivity. One possible explanation for the different results is the level of economic development of these countries at the time of the study Martin and Yang (2009). Most research papers say that exporting will increase the productivity of enterprises regardless of the mechanism of the hypothesis.

In addition, some studies suggest that free trade hinders budget growth of enterprises in developing countries due to lack of comparative advantage, poor competition, and failure to learn from trends. of the world (Young 1991) or find no evidence of the effect of exports on firm's budget in both mechanisms (Wernerfelt, 1984; Greenaway et al., 2005; Sharma and Mishra, 2015). The effect of exports can therefore be mixed results for developing countries with low technical and productivity levels, as is the case with Vietnam.

In Vietnam, recent studies on the relationship between exports and productivity have produced mixed results. According to Vu (2012) studied the effect of export activities and productivity of SMEs in the period 2005-2009 using panel data with fixed effects model and regression model combining endogenous treatment with industrial variables. tool. The results indicate that firms with higher productivity will participate in export activities and the study does not find evidence of learning through export or in other words participating in export activities. have an impact on technical efficiency, technical progress, and changes in production scale. Newman et al (2014) again show that exports have a positive effect on productivity even when self-selection is controlled. The authors find a positive relationship between exports and productivity that can be explained by the effects on the process and quality of innovation.

2.5. Non-wage welfare policies and effects on labor productivity

Human capital is considered to be the main factor driving productivity differences between workers and between firms (Becker, 1975; Koch & McGrath, 1996).

According to Yanadori and Kato (2007) the first theories divide human resources into two categories: general human capital and specific human capital. General human capital is a type of human capital regardless of the type of organization, any organization within the economy can exploit human resources with this level of capital based on formal vocational education and training of the country. entire economy. On the other hand, the human capital of the enterprise, which consists of knowledge (e.g., know-how) and skills specific to the business, acquired through accumulation of experience in the company, training specific to the enterprise. , the company's own treatment regime. Unlike general human capital, enterprise-specific human capital only improves worker productivity for a given business. Usually, this source of capital is mainly used to evaluate wages, benefits, and job requirements (Milkovich & Newman, 1996). Recently, the resource-based view of the enterprise (Barney, 1991) has led human resource management researchers to recognize the role of human capital, especially the firm's own human capital, in improving organizational effectiveness (Pfeffer, 1994) and

the positive effect of human capital on organizational performance will be most evident in labor productivity (Datta et al., 2005).

The enterprise resource-based view basically holds that an internal enterprise's own resources that are not easily transferred to other enterprises will create a source of sustainable competitive advantage. The company's human capital is only valid for certain specific businesses and thus its non-transferable nature creates a barrier to other businesses from obtaining this particular resource (Yanadori and Kato, 2007).

Research into the theory of effective wages and human resource management hypothesizes that higher wages, bonuses, and other compensation programs are important for improving corporate performance through two recruitment channels. employ more qualified and relevant staff, retain better performers, and encourage workers to put in more effort and develop accompanying skills (Shapiro and Stiglitz, 1984; Besley and McLaren, 1993; Lazear, 2000). A better understanding of these two channels through which incentives affect worker productivity will enable companies to design optimal recruitment and compensation strategies to maximize worker productivity and reduce the need for screeners. Filtering is expensive (Oyer & Schaefer, 2010).

Performance-based compensation policies that serve as a component of a larger and more effective set of human resource management (HRM) are associated with better corporate performance in developed countries (Black & Lynch 2001, 2004; Bloom and Van Reenen, 2010; Syverson 2011).

According to the Towers Perrin model (Armstrong, 2010), the remuneration system is divided into two parts, including tangible rewards (purely financial) and intangible rewards. Purely financial rewards such as cash (e.g. salary) are easy to imitate in the business community but intangible or non-financial rewards such as welfare policies cannot or be easily captured. imitate, copy and thus create a unique human resource advantage for the organization.

Typically, compensation schemes are intended to provide a reward in return for an individual's performance in the business. However, benefits, which are one of the components of compensation, are provided to reflect the association of a business with its employees, not just the performance or contribution of the individual. workers (Williams and MacDermid, 1994). Perhaps for this reason there are few studies investigating the effects of welfare regimes on individual or firm performance. However, it is important to understand its impact on individual or business productivity as the welfare share of total compensation packages is trending upward worldwide (Kang, Yu and Lee, 2016) and its own advantages in terms of human resources for organizations and businesses.

3. Discussion and conclusion

Research on labor productivity has important implications for both public policy and decisions for the private sector (Sauermaun, 2016) because it is an important indicator reflecting the effectiveness of a country's economic development. families, businesses and the quality of workers. More specifically, in the context of Vietnam, in the past two decades, although Vietnam's labor productivity has increased rapidly, it is still at the bottom level of ASEAN. New Year catches up with other countries in the region (ILO, 2015). In addition, with the rapid aging of the population, the deeper and deeper integration of the economy, boosting labor productivity is the only and most appropriate way to help Vietnam overcome challenges and welcome challenges. open to new opportunities (ILO, 2015, 2018; Bodewig and Magnusson, 2014).

Promoting labor productivity of the economy first needs to promote labor productivity of enterprises. There are three main groups of factors that help determine labor productivity including: human capital, technological progress and economies of scale (Greelaw et al., 2018). A better understanding of how these factors impact labor productivity helps businesses generate greater profits, increase productivity, increase investment opportunities and reduce costs (ILO, 2015). In this thesis, special attention is paid to two channels affecting labor productivity: technological progress through economic integration, human capital through employee welfare.

Trade liberalization affects labor productivity through various channels including trade openness, exposure to capital and new technologies through FDI, and learning from exports (Rahmah Ismail et al. associates, 2011).

Vietnam's economic integration is deepening and deepening, so there have been many domestic studies on the influence of technology application channels from abroad through FDI and exports on productivity (Xuan, NT & Xing, 2008; Nguyen Khac Minh & Nguyen Viet Hung, 2012; Ngo Hoang Thao Trang, 2017; Pham The Anh, 2018; Hoang and Pham, 2010; Nguyen, KM and Nguyen VH, 2012). Technology adoption by developing economies like Vietnam through globalization regimes has been demonstrated from theoretical models (Findlay, 1978; Romer, 1994; Chen and Shimomura, 1998) to experimental studies in Vietnam mentioned above. Therefore, there is little doubt about the role of technology adoption in developing economies. A more related issue is the choice of how to apply technology in accordance with business characteristics to promote efficiency. For enterprises that often have limited resources like Vietnamese enterprises, in some cases they cannot pursue both strategies to attract FDI and expand exports, which strategy is appropriate? more relevant than the question to be answered.

Enterprises with different levels of capital intensity will have different strategies to pursue when they want to join the globalization mechanism. Choosing which strategy to participate in to get the best benefits is also a problem for SMEs in the current globalization period. One of the research gaps that this thesis wants to fill is to provide empirical evidence on the difference between the two channels of technology application, FDI and export, when it comes to labor productivity in Vietnamese enterprises with different levels of capital intensity.

The second channel affecting labor productivity that the thesis is interested in here is human capital through employee welfare policy. Remuneration policies that have been studied mainly in Vietnam are still wage issues and have proved ineffective in recent years, while compensation policies are related to intangible or non-financial rewards. It is impossible or not easy to imitate, copy creates its own advantage in terms of human resources for the organization but has not been given due attention. There have not been many studies examining the impact of these benefits on the labor productivity of Vietnamese enterprises, especially for SMEs, which account for more than 90% of all enterprises in Vietnam.

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